

Simultaneous Spectrophotometric Determination of Rhodium and Platinum with Sodium-*p*-(mercaptoacetamido) Benzene Sulphonate

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Sodium-*p*-(mercaptoacetamido)benzene sulphonate has been used for the simultaneous spectrophotometric determination of rhodium(III) and platinum(IV) in presence of reasonable amounts of zinc(II), manganese(II), cobalt(II), nickel(II), copper(II), cadmium(II), mercury(II), ruthenium(III), and iridium(III). Palladium interferes in the determination.

Berg and Roebing¹ introduced thionalide as an interesting analytical reagent. It possesses marked precipitating action towards cations that are precipitated as sulphides in acid, neutral and alkaline media. If naphthyl radical in thionalide is replaced by phenyl, then the precipitating action of the resulting thioglycolic acid anilide is similar, but the sensitivity of the precipitations is less². Sulphonic acid derivative of the latter compound, namely, sodium-*p*-(mercaptoacetamido) benzene sulphonate (I), is water soluble and gives water-soluble coloured complexes with metals. It has been reported as a spectrophotometric reagent for cobalt³, nickel⁴ and palladium⁵ by Sogani *et al.*

This compound does not give colour reactions with rhodium (III) and platinum (IV) at room temperature, but on heating the reaction mixture in dilute acidic medium, rhodium develops a brown-yellow and platinum an intense yellow water-soluble colour. This has been made the basis for the simultaneous spectrophotometric determination of these metals by using spectrophotometric equations worked out.

EXPERIMENTAL

Reagent Solution : The method given by Guha Sircar⁶ for preparing thioglycolanilides consists in refluxing an aromatic amine with mercaptoacetic acid between 110 and 120° in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide. Sulphanilic acid is not acylated under these conditions, because the basic character of the amino group is completely masked by the presence of an acidic sulphonic group. However, its sodium salt can be easily acylated. The details of the method are given by Gupta and Sogani³. 1.0% w/v solution of sodium-*p*-(mercaptoacetamido)benzene sulphonate in distilled water was prepared fresh each time.

1. R. Berg and W. Roebing, *Z. Angew. Chem.*, 1935, **48**, 430, 597.
2. F. Feigl, "The Chemistry of Specific, Selective and Sensitive Reactions", Academic Press, New York, 1949, p. 238.
3. H. K. L. Gupta and N. C. Sogani, *Anal. Chem.*, 1959, **31**, 918.
4. J. P. C. Jaimini, M. R. Bhandari and N. C. Sogani, *Jour. and Proc. Inst. Chem.*, 1965, **37**, 162.
5. H. K. L. Gupta, M. R. Bhandari and N. C. Sogani, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1967, **40**, 215.
6. R. M. Misra and S. S. Guha Sircar, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **32**, 127.

Standard Rhodium and Platinum Solutions : Approximately 1 g. of rhodium (III) chloride was dissolved in little water containing 5 ml. of concentrated hydrochloric acid and the volume was then made to 500 ml. It was standardised by using 2-thiobarbituric acid⁷. Platinum (IV) chloride, prepared similarly, was standardised by using ammonium chloride. These were diluted to give solutions containing 25 p.p.m. of the metal.

Buffer Solutions : 10% v/v hydrochloric acid and 10% w/v sodium acetate were used for adjusting the pH.

Instruments : Absorbance measurements were made with a Beckmann Quartz Spectrophotometer, Model DU, using 1.00 cm. cells. pH measurements were made with a Cambridge Bench-Type pH Meter.

Spectral curves of Rhodium and Platinum complexes : 5 ml. of standard rhodium or platinum solution was pipetted in a small beaker. Suitable quantities of 10% v/v hydrochloric acid and 10% w/v sodium acetate were added so that the pH of the final solution was at about 3.5. 5 ml. of 1.0% reagent solution was added and the beaker was kept on a boiling water-bath for about an hour. It was cooled to room temperature, transferred to 25 ml. flask and then volume made upto the mark. Blank reagent solution was also prepared in a similar way. Absorbance of rhodium or platinum complex was measured at different wave-lengths using reagent as blank.

Fig. 1, curve I gives the spectral characteristics of rhodium complex, curve II, of platinum complex and curve III of the reagent solution. Reagent solution has an absorbance upto 330 m μ , hence, to avoid interference, estimations were done using reagent as blank solution.

Fig 1: Absorbance curves pH-3.0, I-Rhodium complex (Rh-5 ppm), II - Platinum complex (Pt=5 ppm), III-Reagent (4 ppm).

Effect of pH : The range of constant maximum for rhodium complex is between 2.5 and 5.2 and for platinum complex is between 2.2 and 4.5. Hence, all estimations were done at about pH 3.0.

Effect of Heating : The complete development of colour for rhodium complex took nearly 45 min. and for platinum complex, nearly 15 min. The colour was not affected on longer heating.

Reagent Ratio for maximum absorbance : For full development of colour, 1 : 60 ratio of rhodium to reagent and 1 : 75 ratio of platinum to reagent is required. It appears that considerable amount of the reagent is consumed in reducing these metals to the bivalent state, which then forms complex with the reagent.

Recommended Procedure for simultaneous determination of Rhodium and Platinum : An aliquot, which contains rhodium and platinum in an amount that will give an absorbance in the range of 0.2 to 0.8; is taken in a small beaker. 10% hydrochloric acid and 10% sodium acetate solutions are added to bring the pH between 2.5 and 3.5. 5 ml. of 1% reagent solution is then added and it is kept on a boiling water-bath for about an hour. It is cooled to room temperature, transferred to 25 ml. flask and volume made up to the mark. Absorbance is measured at 300 and 360 $m\mu$ using reagent as blank.

Experiments have shown that absorbance values of rhodium and platinum complexes are quantitatively additive in nature. Rhodium and platinum content is calculated by using spectrophotometric equations given in Table II. Table I gives the values of extinction of rhodium and platinum complexes at wave-lengths 300 and 360 $m\mu$. These values have been used to calculate⁸ equations for determination of these metals.

TABLE I

Extinction of metal complexes

		300 $m\mu$	360 $m\mu$
Extinction of rhodium complex, 1 ppm	Rh	0.076	0.105
Extinction of platinum complex, 1 ppm	Pt	0.100	0.046

TABLE II

Spectrophotometric equations used

$$\text{Rhodium, ppm} = 14.28 A_{360} - 6.58 A_{300}$$

$$\text{Platinum, ppm} = 15.00 A_{300} - 10.85 A_{360}$$

where A_{300} and A_{360} are absorbance values obtained experimentally at 300 and 360 $m\mu$ respectively.

A series of synthetic samples containing rhodium, platinum and diverse ions were analysed by the procedure given above and the results are given in Table III. Palladium interferes in the determination of these metals. Sodium-*p*-(mercaptoacetamido) benzene sulphonate is a useful reagent for the routine analysis of rhodium and platinum.

8. E. B. Sandell, "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals", 3rd Ed., Interscience, New York, 1959, p. 103.

TABLE III

Analysis of synthetic samples

Added ppm		Diverse ions ppm	Found ppm	
Rh	Pt		Rh	Pt
2.50	2.50	—	2.45	2.56
2.00	3.00	—	2.02	2.98
1.50	3.50	—	1.52	3.56
3.50	1.50	—	3.56	1.54
2.00	3.00	30 Zn(II)	2.06	2.98
2.00	3.00	30 Mn(II)	2.02	2.97
2.00	3.00	15 Co(II)	2.04	2.96
2.00	3.00	20 Ni(II)	2.05	3.02
2.00	3.00	20 Cu(II)	1.98	3.04
2.00	3.00	40 Cd(II)	1.97	3.06
2.00	3.00	30 Hg(II)	2.00	3.03
2.00	3.00	2 Ru(III)	2.02	2.98
2.00	3.00	10 Ir(III)	2.04	2.97

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